

**АБЫЛАЙ ХАН АТЫНДАҒЫ ҚАЗАҚ ХАЛЫҚАРАЛЫҚ ҚАТЫНАСТАР
ЖӘНЕ ӘЛЕМ ТІЛДЕРІ УНИВЕРСИТЕТІ**

**КАЗАХСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ
И МИРОВЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ ИМЕНИ АБЫЛАЙ ХАНА**

**KAZAKH ABLAI KHAN UNIVERSITY OF
INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS AND WORLD LANGUAGES**

**«Аударматану және филология саласындағы
мәдениаралық қарым-қатынас мәселелері»
X студенттік ғылыми-практикалық конференцияның мақалалар
ЖИНАҒЫ**

**СБОРНИК
статей X студенческой научно-практической конференции
«Вопросы межкультурной коммуникации
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Аскарбекова Ж.,
студент факультета Перевода и Филологии
КазУМОиМЯ имени Абылай хана
Алматы, Казахстан
e-mail: jenny.ask1412@gmail.com

АФФЕКТИВНЫЕ КОНЦЕПТЫ И СПОСОБЫ ИХ ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ РОМАНА Ф.М. ДОСТОЕВСКОГО “БРАТЬЯ КАРАМАЗОВЫ”

В данной статье проводится анализ аффективных концептов, отраженных в вербальных и невербальных решениях персонажей романа Ф.М. Достоевского «Братья Карамазовы». Цель исследования - определить возникновение и влияние аффективных концептов на действия и реакции участников коммуникативной ситуации. Аффективные концепты рассматриваются в соответствии с выбором слов и их связью с эмоциональным и контекстуальным происхождением. В частности, анализ был проведен путем рассмотрения позитивно и негативно валентных концептуальных состояний, таких как «волнение», «благодарность», «отчаяние» и «агрессия».

Ключевые слова: аффективный концепт, коммуникация, коммуникативная ситуация, концептуализация, вербальные взаимодействия.

Askarbekova J.,
Student of Translation and Philology of Ablai khan
KazUIR&WL, Almaty, Kazakhstan
e-mail: jenny.ask1412@gmail.com

AFFECTIVE CONCEPTS AND WAYS OF THEIR EXPRESSION ON THE BASIS OF F.M. DOSTOEVSKY'S “THE BROTHERS KARAMAZOV”

This article analyses affective concepts reflected in the verbal and non-verbal decisions of the characters in F.M. Dostoevsky's novel “The Brothers Karamazov”. The aim of the study is to determine the occurrence and the influence of affects on the actions and reactions of participants in a communicative situation. In the paper, the affective concepts are considered in accordance with the word selection and their connection with emotional and contextual origin. Particularly, the analysis was conducted by considering positive and negative valence conceptual states such as “excitement”, “gratitude”, “despair” and “aggression”.

Key words: affective concept, communication, communicative situation, conceptualization, verbal interactions.

Introduction

When discussing on the means of focus of the communication studies, language is the one of the primary concepts that appears on the surface. Language, while being used in the communicative situation serves both function of producing the knowledge of the participants and the function of receiving it, thereby it depends on the conditions the participants are in. However, the result of such verbal communications is the meaning of words as a result of the collision of meanings of words during verbal interaction. In this way, concepts are generated. A concept is a semantic formation, marked by linguistic and cultural specificity, which thus characterize the speakers [1, pp. 4-5]. The concept includes emotional, expressive, evaluative and other expressions [1, pp. 243-244]. One of the aspects of the concept of emotion is affective phenomena. From the perspective of linguistics, affective concepts can be analysed in accordance of the ways of language being used to convey emotions and attitudes. In particular, communication studies are interested in how the speaker brings those emotions into utterances, as well as the listener's perception of those utterances while evoking emotions in return. According to L.F. Barrett, it is worth noting that every word carries with it an individual's experience, and as such, has the potential to elicit emotional responses and mental states [2, p.27]. To examine the potential emotional affective concepts, this paper analyses verbal interactions of the individual's characters and how they influence or are influenced by those experiences through Fyodor Dostoyevsky's *The Brothers Karamazov* novel as an example to illustrate the role played by positive/negative affects in decision making, character shaping, and theme revealing.

Materials and Methods

It is widely accepted that affective states can be judged depending on their valence dimension. Valence refers to individual's evaluation of the experience from positive to negative. A. Wierzbicka defines emotion concepts on the basis of cognitive scenarios, i.e. "something good happened" / "something bad happened" and related concepts. Noting that every language has a word for "feeling" and that languages have words that link feeling to thinking, she then proposes verbal behavioural universals in terms of affective concepts. In this regard, positive and negative affective states may vary across cultures, and some cultures may not even define certain conditions as positive or negative [3].

A. Positive affective concepts.

A concept of positive affect is a measure of the level of enthusiasm, activity and alertness that an individual feels when engaged in pleasurable activities [4, p.1063]. For instance, an interaction between Fyodor Pavlovich Karamazov and the Elder Zosima (Book 2, Chapter 2), in which the affective state is driven by Elder's gentle advice: "*Не стесняйтесь, будьте совершенно как дома. А главное, не стыдитесь столь самого себя, ибо от сего лишь всё и выходит.*" The statement elicits a response due to the wide range of emotions it evokes in Fyodor Pavlovich's nature as a blithing character. This leads to a turn-taking dialogue, with Zosima as the producer and trigger of the dissolute landowner's affective state: "*Совершенно как дома? То есть в натуральном-то виде? О, этого много, слишком много, но — с умилением принимаю! Знаете, благословенный отец, вы меня на натуральный-то вид не вызывайте, не рискуйте... до натурального вида я и сам не дойду. Это я, чтобы вас охранить, предупреждаю.*" Although all interaction is cooperative, Fyodor Pavlovich's character tends to react strongly to the light, expressing his thoughts in a passionate manner and avoiding the usual moments of completion in his speech, thus making it long-winded. In reasoning, he is affected and initially responds driven by such concept as "gratitude". In speech etiquette, gratitude can be described as concept that is present in a socio-cultural phenomenon and operates according to the system of reciprocity, whereby one expresses gratitude for a good deed done or promises to do something in return. This concept is conveyed as a good deed in return, an advice, with the intention of warning the interlocutor.

The speech then proceeds, anchored by the excitement at the wisdom and insight of the Elder: "*Вы меня сейчас замечанием вашим: «Не стыдиться столь самого себя, потому что от сего лишь всё и выходит», — вы меня замечанием этим как бы насквозь прочкнули и внутри прочли.*" In his

speech, the language used to describe the excitement is vivid and coloured by delight. The functional purpose of «excitement» as a concept is to manifest as a heightened state of energy, enthusiasm, and eagerness. Overall, their conversation serves the function of giving the portrayal of his character as the one who tests oneself with the sense of shame and hides it behind buffoonery. As previously mentioned, affective concepts can be analysed based on the language used to convey emotions and attitudes.

It is important for both participants to decode the meaning of each concept evoked in the communicative situation in order to ensure effective communication. However, regulating all behavioural aspects in an affective state is not possible, as it is largely can result in various reactions. In this particular case, reaction is presented in father Karamazov's questioning and remorseful attitude: *“Ведь если б я только был уверен, когда вхожу, что все меня за милейшего и умнейшего человека сейчас же примут, — господи! какой бы я тогда был добрый человек! Учитель! — повергся он вдруг на колени, — что мне делать, чтобы наследовать жизнь вечную?”* This expands the roles of both characters in their nature and picture of the world, highlighting their differences by verbal and nonverbal systems that operate together as part of the larger communication process.

Whereas the dialogue occurs in one of the first chapters, the positive affect here serves to contrastively reveal the beliefs and mindsets of Elder Zosima and Fyodor Pavlovich. The presence of an affective state in a character reflects their degree of involvement in the narrative, depending on the dialogue's structural composition. An emotional state comprises a response that corresponds to emotional experiences, often displayed non-verbally to reinforce verbal communication, it portrays how the affect can undergo changes from one emotion to another, especially with the enthusiasm and impetuosity, both in action and reaction, are the properties of a character; in our case Fyodor Karamazov.

B. Negative affective concepts.

D. Watson points out that the negative affect can be defined as a broad dimension of subjective distress and unpleasurable engagement that encompasses various aversive mood states [4, p.1063]. If a state is in the negative conceptual field, it can produce aggression as one of possible reactions. Further analysis of negative affective state of the characters of Dmitry Karamazov in the letter to Katerina Ivanovna, which she submitted as proof of Mitya's guilt to Ivan Fyodorovich (Book 11, Chapter 7), follows the concept “aggression” and “desperation”: *“...Завтра буду доставать у всех людей, а не достану у людей, то даю тебе честное слово, пойду к отцу и проломлю ему голову и возьму у него под подушкой, только бы уехал Иван. В каторгу пойду, а три тысячи отдам. А сама прощай. Кланяюсь до земли, ибо пред тобой подлец. Прости меня.”* It is important to remember the impulsive nature of Dmitry's character and the fact that the letter was written in a state of intoxication. In terms of an affect, his condition quickly shifts from a strongly negative expression to a weakly negative part. The relationship between Mitya and Katerina cannot be described as unambiguous; he interprets her actions with contempt, which is reflected in his subjectively deciphered interpretation of her intentions, thus responded in a form of an apology, a promise to pay in return and riddance. This already implies a sharpness and contrast in stylistic choice in words displayed as the state of a desperate character, where his aggression is only focused on his father and not towards Katya, to whom he expresses his own respect.

Feelings of anger and desperation are moreover forming Dmitry's word selection, as he then repeats them in the later addition to the letter: *“... Убью себя, а сначала все-таки пса. Вырву у него три и брошу тебе. Хоть подлец пред тобой, а не вор! Жди трех тысяч. У пса под тюфяком, розовая ленточка. Не я вор, а вора моего убью. Катя, не гляди презрительно: Димитрий не вор, а убийца! Отца убил и себя погубил, чтобы стоять и гордости твоей не выносить. И тебя не любить.”* F. Bergamino describes Mitya's furious intentions as “the reactive response to feeling deceived by those who, for his whole life, were indifferent to his existence and now take advantage of his impulsivity in order to deprive him of the inheritance that belongs to him” [5, p.238]. Such communicative behaviour may be associated with a close connection between the emotions and experiences of the character, which, in turn, is most likely due to the circumstances of his life and for this reason, he refers to Fyodor Karamazov as a thief and a deceiver. Thus, the mere mention

of his father can elicit in Dmitry an affective state caused by a series of provocative and unpleasant associations transforming into an explicit state taking a verbal form.

The affective state focuses on emotions, but the presentation of these emotions directly depends on Dmitry's experience. We can conclude about the character of Mitya and his interaction with other characters in a communicative situation, depending on which impression will become an agent for the affective state. It can be seen in a stylistic choice that indicates how the character's nature remains closely connected with peripheral associations with his father, which were formed as a result of difficult experiences and manifest themselves in the form of negative affective feelings, therefore revealing their uncontrollability depending on the subject matter.

Furthermore, the concept of "aggression" could be exemplified by observing the behaviour of the character Ivan Karamazov when he is engaged in a conversation with the Devil (Book 11, Chapter 9). It is important to indicate the context of the following communicative situation: Ivan Fedorovich is suffering from disturbing stress and fever, which he is aware of, as well as he is aware of potential hallucinations: *"Ни одной минуты не принимаю тебя за реальную правду, — как-то яростно даже вскричал Иван. — Ты ложь, ты болезнь моя, ты призрак. Я только не знаю, чем тебя истребить, и вижу, что некоторое время надобно протраждать. ..."* The dismissive and declarative mood reflects the negative perception of an unexpected guest, compounded by the stress of his brother's upcoming trial and his own illness, those feelings shape his aggressive before being produced in the discursive form of speech interaction.

To gain a more accurate understanding of Ivan's aggressive affect, it is essential to note how R.F. Baumeister et al. suggest that negative emotions may be more fully represented in language due to their perceived importance and power, which may explain why there are more words for negative emotions than positive ones. As a result, negative experiences such as bad emotions, bad parenting, and bad feedback may have a greater impact than positive emotions, and negative information may be processed more thoroughly than positive information [6, pp. 331-337]. Based on this information, it can be concluded that the paternal figure in the Karamazov family left its mark on the brothers' growth even without constant involvement of their father, which is why there is such a resemblance in speech style between the Devil and Fyodor Pavlovich, especially in the regular use of French expressions and the tendency to quote. The presence of such experiential figure affects Ivan's attitude, expressing Ivan's displeasure both in the resemblance of the Gentleman and in his presence: *"Иван Федорович злобно молчал и не хотел заговаривать."*

Moreover, Ivan shows his displeasure by regularly referring to the Gentleman as a fool, treat him with scepticism and even scold his reasoning; it can be underlined by observing Ivan reacting on the Devil's utterance *"Мне нравится, что мы с тобой прямо стали на ты, — начал было гость."* and interrupting him, thus breaking the speech etiquette and confirming his verbal expressions of the dignified emotion of anger with non-verbal ones: *"Дурак, — засмеялся Иван, — что ж я вы, что ли, стану тебе говорить. ..."* Literary writers excel at withholding information of the character's relations from readers and creating suspense. Describing nonverbal behaviours allow readers to speculate about the characters' inner world. In this case, Ivan Fyodorovich's passive aggression is conveyed through the systemic formal/informal etiquette 'ТЫ-ВЫ' in the Russian language, which is used to evaluate respect towards the interlocutor. In this regard, Ivan demonstrates his lack of respect for the Gentlemen. In social communication, the lack of respect often leads to inappropriate conflict resolution. This is exemplified by the Ivan's transition from passive-aggressive to active-aggressive behaviour later on: *"Гость говорил, очевидно увлекаясь своим красноречием, всё более и более возвышая голос и насмешливо поглядывая на хозяина; но ему не удалось докончить: Иван вдруг схватил со стола стакан и с размаху пустил в оратора."*

The emotional response to the concept of "aggression" is evident in this passage through the disregard for speech etiquette. This violation hinders effective communication, even if the dialogue is interpreted as a profound reflection, all that because the true intentions of both participants in the communicative situation did not reach a consensus, resulting in no common conclusion. Ivan

Karamazov's emotional state disrupts the basic turn-taking structure of communication, highlighting how one character's emotions can impact the communication strategies of another character, such as the Devil, who adjusts his style and word choice to the presumed interests, relevance and knowledge of Ivan Fyodorovich.

Results in Discussion

Reviewed above research data emphasize that concept and affect are closely related due to their direct connection with human experience and the collection of information on each subject matter. Affect refers to the emotional response to an associative experience with an object, while a concept is the result of an associative experience with other concepts that have a semantic or lexical relation within the conceptual field. Fyodor Dostoevsky utilises his characters' experiences to illustrate the impact of these experiences on their actions and thought processes during communication. The author illustrates how a positive emotional state can enhance communication and social connections, while a negative emotional state can influence the dialogue of his characters, revealing their relationship to each other and their reaction to the events in which they are involved.

Thus, an affective state may arise simply from referencing a concept that holds emotional relevance to an individual, i.e. in a communicative situation it has a producer or trigger that prompts the subject to feel controlled or uncontrolled emotions. The speaker uses words to express these emotions, which forms a discursive form of speech interaction, in which the turn-taking system regulates the change of action and reaction. In this regard, it is also worth noting, that turn-taking conversation structure can be disrupted as a result of ineffective interaction, in which either the speaker or the listener does not understand the essence of the feelings hidden behind the words. This may occur in a situation where both participants are unable to read each other's intentions in their dialogue, because words may undergo changes in their tone.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the importance of the emotional aspect of an individual's picture of the world determines the existence of a diverse group of affective concepts, which serves to express emotions and emotional evaluations of the topic raised in speech and, thus reflect a person's inner world. Understanding the influence of affective concepts on human language use can help listeners and readers better interpret the mood or feelings of others, leading to more effective communication as a result.

The studied materials testify to the small study of affective concepts of emotions. In this paper, attention was paid to only several of them. However, the given conceptual analysis is indicative and somewhat contribute the existing gap of affective concepts analyses and complements interest for future researches.

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Бекзалбекова Д.,

студент факультета Перевода и Филологии

КазУМОиМЯ имени Абылай хана

Алматы, Казахстан

e-mail: bekzalbekova@mail.ru

Научный руководитель:

PhD, Курманбаева Д.Т.

КазУМОиМЯ имени Абылай хана

e-mail: dametken1971@mail.ru

КОНЦЕПТ “ВЛАСТЬ” И ЕГО РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ПРЕССЕ

Язык, как основной инструмент коммуникации, отражает и формирует восприятие власти, захватывая сложные социокультурные нюансы и динамику того, как этот концепт воспринимается. В этой статье проводится анализ концепта «Власть», представленного в современной английской прессе. Цель статьи – проанализировать лингвистическую репрезентацию концепта «Власть» в современной английской прессе. Анализ двух статей показал, что концепт представлен различными лексемами, такими как «влиятельный», «твердая власть» и «мягкая власть», отражая различные измерения власти, обсуждаемые в прессе.

Ключевые слова: власть, когнитивная лингвистика, концептуальный анализ, английская пресса, значение.

Bekzalbekova D.,

student of Translation and Philology of Ablai khan

KazUIR&WL, Almaty, Kazakhstan

e-mail: bekzalbekova@mail.ru

Scientific supervisor:

Kurmanbayeva D.T., PhD, Ablai khan KazUIRandWL,

Almaty, Kazakhstan, e-mail: dametken1971@mail.ru

THE CONCEPT “POWER” AND ITS REPRESENTATION IN CONTEMPORARY ENGLISH PRESS

Language, as the primary tool of communication, reflects and shapes perceptions of power, capturing complex sociocultural nuances and the dynamics of how this concept is perceived. This article analyses concept of “Power” represented in the contemporary English press. The aim of the study is to explore the linguistic representation of the concept of “Power” in contemporary English press. The analysis of two newspaper articles showed that the concept is represented by various lexemes such as “influential,” “hard power,” and “soft power”, reflecting different dimensions of power discussed in the press.

Key words: power, cognitive linguistics, conceptual analysis, English press, meaning.

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050022, г. Алматы, ул. Муратбаева, 200
e-mail: kazumo@ablaikhan.kz, ablaikhan@list.ru